

CORRECTIVE-LOGOPEDIC TECHNIQUES TO CURE SPEECH FLAWS IN YOUNG INFANTS WITH UNDERDEVELOPED SPEECH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8142811>

Annotation: This page discusses the reasons of speech flaws in children whose speech has not fully developed, crises that arise at various ages for the child, the ways in which speech defects appear, and the system of corrective and speech therapy for their eradication.

Key words: Language, crisis, age periods, emotional expressiveness, defect, autonomous speech, communication, vocabulary, reserve, speech, speech defects.

Language is a social phenomenon. The mother tongue of every nation living in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a bright indicator of its national identity and spiritual culture. The connection between speech and thinking is not only psychological not only in the deep stages of processes, but also at the level of social events. The influence of words on a person and his behavior is well known to everyone. "Although language and thinking cannot live without each other, they do not represent the same phenomenon. Thought is the culmination of objective existence, and language is a means of expression, giving and strengthening thoughts to other people. Words and concepts require each other dialogically.

Currently, there are two trends in the interaction between languages in our country: on the one hand, the further development and improvement of national languages, and on the other hand, the importance of the Uzbek language as a state language is increasing. The independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the economic needs made it necessary to learn the Uzbek language, the mother tongue of a large number of the country's population, as the state language, which

and it acquires great social importance in the conditions of a multi-ethnic society.

A child's life is integrated into the life and activities of adults. But despite this, at the same time, the child does not have any of the unique human means of influencing them. This determines the main hereditary (genetic) task at this stage of development, that is, the task of forming methods and means of communicating with adults in babies. Emotional-indirect communication is the main type of activity at this age.

Isolation of a child, lack of emotional connections with adults can lead to his insufficient development from the first months of his life.

At the age of infancy, the child's communication especially with adults develops rapidly, initial affection is formed, social expectations are formed (the child expects actions from adults that are suitable for certain life situations), the first forms of partnership between the child and adults begin to form. Although the child can't do anything, he can do the actions of adults

learns to manage. This happens regardless of the fact that speech does not yet exist. He has only voice and gestures at his disposal. The first words are emotional expressiveness, relevance to the situation and

is distinguished by its communicative orientation. Such speech is called autonomous or situational speech, it is understandable only to relatives who are familiar with the environment around the child. The initial understanding of the word is combined with the acceptance of a certain situation. The first words refer to specific things and do not have a generalizing feature (watch means only clocks hanging on the wall). The word takes place in the general view of the child's behavior and it leads to the expression of a one-word thought together with gestures, hand movements, glances, expressive means ("Goodbye", "Give", "Take").

The emergence of the first words is a social aspect of child development indicates that the situation has changed. Now the child himself can express his wishes, and adults have the opportunity to direct his behavior with the help of verbal instructions. it can be called the perception of the attitude of adults towards him. A positive attitude towards oneself is the basis for the normal development of a person.

A negative attitude towards oneself is the result of a child's lack of emotional and positive communication with adults at an early age.

Communication with the child should be built on the basis of cooperation with him. Constant forcing of adults to do something creates in the child not the desire to actively research and learn, but laziness, only the desire to adapt to the environment.

In the period from one to three years, the social situation regarding child development changes significantly. Together with the adults who are their relatives, the circle of communication of the child includes other adults who should first of all satisfy the need of attention and care of the child (employees of educational institutions, teaching assistants). they start coming. In such conditions, children of the first age with adults

the need to communicate about objects, toys and the actions that should be performed with them increases. A child of this age develops the ability to establish emotional and practical relationships with adults, which helps him adapt to new life conditions: evaluates words, requests helps to correctly perceive thoughts and emotional relationships of other people.

When a child arrives at a preschool educational institution, his emotional connections in the "child-adult" relationship system are joined by the "child-peer" relationship.

In the third year of a child's life, babies begin to actively imitate each other, strive to show themselves, and at the same time begin to feel the attitude towards themselves, the first speech dialogues appear. In children of the first age, children's society is just beginning to form. They spend most of their free time in close proximity to each other playing games alone. Game communities created by children's initiative - dyads (playing in pairs) are not stable. The child's self-evaluation is emotionally painted in bright colors, and he is a good child. It is related to meeting the demands of adults and seeking their approval.

At the end of the first year of a child's life, children make general evaluations about themselves: "good", "big", etc. By the age of three, the "I" system is formed. Through the child's identity ("I'm Yulduzkhan", "I'm Kamronbek"), he tries to get his ideas about what gender he belongs to (boy, girl), approval, recognition ("I'm good") and includes the need for independence ("I am myself").

The central innovation in three-year-old children is the emergence of the "ME" system, which, in turn, creates the need to act on the child's own initiative, elements of voluntary behavior. The formation of the "MEN" system results in self-evaluation and the desire to meet the requirements of adults. It is recommended to have entertainment in the form of games and performances. They should be not only entertaining, but also educational.

Tasks related to the development of the speech of a three-year-old child:

- support the child's ability to engage in active communication with the means of speech beyond the range of possibilities, to respond to the questions and suggestions of adults, to express his wishes, feelings, thoughts and to express his opinion by taking the initiative;

- encourage their interest in the work of their peers, their desire to share their impressions with them, their interest in game actions, their interest in expressing their reaction to the happening event in speech;

- expand your child's vocabulary about people, plants, food, clothes, furniture, pets, toys, objects (shirt sleeves, pockets and collars; car door wheels, etc.) enrich with names. Pay special attention to teaching how to connect words correctly in a sentence (for example, "He went home", not "He went home", "I will go today", not "Yesterday");

- to teach children to pronounce vowels and consonants correctly Teach

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